

The Role of Chemical Structure and Medium in the Reducibility of some Aromatic Aldehydes

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The electrochemical reduction of benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde and anisaldehyde was investigated at metallurgical copper and electrolytic cadmium cathodes in aqueous ethanol (1 : 1) containing 0.25 M H₂SO₄. It was found that the reducibility of the aldehydes studied follows the order, anisaldehyde > salicylaldehyde > benzaldehyde. The influence of the medium (acidic, basic and neutral) on the reduction process has been investigated. All the aldehydes possess the highest reducibility in acidic medium and the lowest one in basic medium. The effect of concentration of both acid and base on the reduction process has also been investigated. The potential measurements were carried out using galvanostatic technique. The Tafel's slope and the order of the overall electrode process in acidic medium have been evaluated.

MANY authors¹⁻⁵ studied the reduction of carbonyl compounds using different cathodes. Carbonyl compounds can be reduced in one-electron route to give pinacols, in two-electron process to give an alcohol or by four-electron mechanism to produce hydrocarbon⁶. The activity of carbonyl compounds towards electrochemical reduction is highly dependent on their structure and substituents^{7,8}.

In the present work, we aimed to investigate the effects of chemical structure and medium on the reduction of some aromatic aldehydes.

Experimental

The electrolytic cell used consisted of two compartments separated by a porous diaphragm of sintered glass. The anode was a platinum sheet of 4.0 cm² surface area while the cathode was made of copper spiral of 5.0 cm² surface area. The electrolytes used have the following compositions: aqueous ethanol (1 : 1) + 0.25 M H₂SO₄ (acidic medium), aqueous ethanol (1 : 1) + 0.25 M NaOH (basic medium), and aqueous ethanol (1 : 1) + 0.25 M Na₂SO₄ (neutral medium). Each cathode was pretreated chemically before every experiment and then kept in solution under investigation for about 10 min without polarising current. Cadmium cathodes were made by electrodeposition on the spiral copper cathodes for 1 h from the following bath⁹: CdSO₄.8/3 H₂O, 65 g dm⁻³; (NH₄)₂SO₄, 35 g dm⁻³; Al₂(SO₄)₃.18H₂O, 30 g dm⁻³; glue, 0.7 g dm⁻³; and C.d., 1.0 A dm⁻².

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and used without further purification.

The current efficiency of reduction (*F*) was taken as a measure for the ease of reduction of the carbonyl function,

$$F = \frac{V - V'}{V} \times 100$$

where, *V* and *V'* are the corrected volumes of hydrogen evolved over the coulometer and the working electrode, respectively. The temperature during electrolysis was kept at 30 ± 0.1°. The cathodic potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode.

Results and Discussion

In the present study the electroreduction of benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde and anisaldehyde was investigated at metallurgical copper and electrolytic cadmium cathodes over a wide ranges of current density and concentration. The effect of current density, concentration and the nature of cathode material on the reduction efficiency had been discussed in previous publications^{4,5,10,11}.

Effect of chemical structure of aldehydes: In acidic medium, the reduction of aldehydes and ketones may proceed via the mechanism,

The reducibility of the studied aldehydes in acidic medium may be arranged in the order, anisal-

dehyde > salicylaldehyde > benzaldehyde. The study was carried out on electrolytic cadmium and metallurgical copper cathodes and the results are shown in Fig. 1. The high reducibility of anisaldehyde could be attributed to the effect of methoxy

Fig. 1. Reduction efficiency of the aldehydes (0.1 M) in acidic medium.

group in *para*-position which stabilises both the carbonium ion and free radical (b) and (c) formed. The stability of these intermediates is known to depend on the aromaticity and the delocalisation of charge density on the radical. In salicylaldehyde, the hydroxyl group stabilises also the intermediates (free radical and carbonium ion) formed to some extent. In this way, the anisaldehyde intermediates are the most stable, while those of benzaldehyde are the least stable ones. This fact must reflect itself on the reducibility of the studied aldehydes.

Polarisation measurements: From the cathodic behaviour of the reduction potentials of the three aldehydes in acidic medium at copper and cadmium cathodes, it was observed that the potential shifted towards more positive values (less cathodic) by

TABLE 1—THE ORDER OF OVERALL ELECTRODE PROCESS DURING REDUCTION OF ALDEHYDES AT DIFFERENT CATHODES

Compd.	Copper cathode		Cadmium cathode	
	$E(V)$	n	$E(V)$	n
Benzaldehyde	0.6	0.145	0.8	0.19
	0.65	0.145	0.9	0.18
	0.7	0.14	1.0	0.165
	0.8	0.115	1.1	0.155
	0.9	0.10	1.2	0.125
Salicylaldehyde	0.5	0.25	0.8	0.31
	0.55	0.22	0.9	0.30
	0.6	0.22	1.0	0.26
	0.7	0.19	1.1	0.255
	0.8	0.19	1.2	0.19
Anisaldehyde	0.5	0.24	0.75	0.35
	0.6	0.26	0.8	0.33
	0.7	0.235	0.9	0.34
	0.8	0.18	1.0	0.29
	0.9	0.19	1.1	0.265

increasing concentration. The concentration of benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde and anisaldehyde affects the overall rate of the cathodic reduction according to the power function,

$$i_{(E)} = KC^n$$

By plotting $\log i$ vs $\log C$, the values of n can be evaluated (Table 1), and it is obvious that the order (n) of the overall electrode process generally decreases by increasing the reduction potential. This could be ascribed to the different contribution of aldehyde reduction to the overall electrode process. At lower potentials, the reduction efficiency of the studied aldehydes is higher than that at higher potential. Thus the contribution of aldehyde in reduction process is greater at lower reduction potentials.

The values of Tafel's slope b_1 (at lower potentials) and b_2 (at higher potentials) have been evaluated (Table 2). The variation of b values (b_1 and b_2) confirms the different nature of both the cathodic processes taking place at low and high potentials. It seems that one-electrode process is vanishing and another one is starting to replace it at relatively higher potentials.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF TAFEL'S CONSTANT (b) FOR REDUCTION OF ALDEHYDES AT COPPER AND CADMIUM CATHODES

Concn. (M)		Benzaldehyde		Salicylaldehyde		Anisaldehyde	
		Cu	Cd	Cu	Cd	Cu	Cd
0.1	b_1	0.10	0.135	0.13	0.165	0.145	0.215
	b_2	0.22	0.28	0.18	0.30	0.19	0.30
0.075	b_1	0.10	0.13	0.125	0.175	0.14	0.19
	b_2	0.205	0.265	0.185	0.285	0.195	0.29
0.05	b_1	0.105	0.145	0.115	0.15	0.13	0.195
	b_2	0.21	0.23	0.165	0.27	0.155	0.27
0.025	b_1	0.095	0.15	0.11	0.16	0.12	0.16
	b_2	0.19	0.225	0.145	0.255	0.155	0.275
0.01	b_1	0.09	0.15	0.10	0.16	0.095	0.145
	b_2	0.165	0.22	0.14	0.215	0.15	0.235

Effect of medium on reduction efficiency: The electrochemical reduction of benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde and anisaldehyde within the concentration range 0.01–0.1 M was carried out at metallurgical copper and electrolytic cadmium cathodes in acidic, basic and neutral media. The results show that the aldehydes possess the highest reduction efficiencies (F) in acidic medium while the lowest values were observed in basic medium at copper and cadmium cathodes. Representative curves for the reduction of anisaldehyde (0.1 M) in the three different media at copper and cadmium cathodes are shown in Fig. 1; the other two studied aldehydes exhibit similar behaviour.

The observed high reduction efficiency (F) of aldehydes in acidic medium with respect to basic and neutral media may be due to the increase of

hydrogen ion concentration from basic to acidic which encourages the protonation of the reducible functional groups. The electrochemical reduction of carbonyl compounds appears to be controlled by the availability of protons in the solvent^{1,2}. Elving and Leone³ reported that the reduction of carbonyl compounds in basic medium is more difficult than that in acidic one which is in accord with our observations. On the other hand, the decrease of hydrogen ion concentration from acidic to basic makes the protonation of reducible functional groups more difficult and accordingly the reducibility decreases.

A representative curves for the cathodic galvanostatic polarisation of anisaldehyde (0.05 M) at cadmium cathode in different media are shown in Fig. 2. The other two aldehydes behave similarly. Fig. 2 reveals that more negative potentials are needed to produce further reduction in basic medium than neutral. Also more negative potential is needed to realise further reduction in neutral

Fig. 2. Cathodic polarization curves of anisaldehyde (0.05 M) in different media.

Fig. 3. Reduction efficiency of anisaldehyde (0.1M) at cadmium and copper electrodes in different media.

than in acidic medium. This must be reflected on the reducibility of aldehydes which is in good accord with our explanation.

The work was also extended to investigate the effect of varying concentration of H₂SO₄ in acid medium and NaOH in basic medium on the reducibility of aldehydes. In acidic medium, the results (Table 3) show that the reduction efficiency increases by increasing acid concentration (up to 1.0 M). Above 1.0 M, the reduction efficiency was found to be independent of acid concentration. The increase in the reducibility with increasing acidity confirms the role played by protons in the reduction process. While at higher concentrations of H₂SO₄ (more than 1.0 M), it seems that the hydrogen discharge becomes easier, and inhibits the whole reduction process^{1,2}. Another factor of significant contribution is the decrease of the mobility of all reaction species as a result of increasing viscosity of the solution as the H₂SO₄ concentration is increased. Accordingly, one can conclude that the chance of contribution of the reducible functions in the cathodic process (its reduction) decreases at high hydrogen ion concentration. On the other hand, the transfer of hydrogen ion from the bulk of solution to cathodic area takes place via different ways.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF ACID CONTENT (M) ON REDUCTION EFFICIENCY (F) OF THE ALDEHYDES (0.05 M) AT 5.0 mA cm⁻²

Compd.	Reduction efficiency (F%)					
	0.25M	0.5M	0.75M	1.0M	1.25M	1.5M
Benzaldehyde	66.2	70.1	73.5	73.7	73.45	74.1
Salicylaldehyde	78.0	81.7	85.2	86.0	86.5	86.8
Anisaldehyde	86.4	90.5	95.0	95.5	95.2	95.1

In basic medium, the increase of NaOH concentration from 0.25 to 1.5 M always leads to relative decrease in the reducibility of aldehydes as shown in Table 4. This behaviour could be ascribed to the low hydrogen ion concentration and for the necessity of a more negative potential to achieve further reduction as mentioned before.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF NaOH CONTENT (M) ON REDUCIBILITY (F) OF THE ALDEHYDES (0.05 M) AT 5 mA cm⁻²

Compd.	Reduction efficiency (F%)					
	0.25M	0.5M	0.75M	1.0M	1.25M	1.5M
Benzaldehyde	45.0	41.2	41.0	38.2	36.7	34.9
Salicylaldehyde	52.1	48.3	46.4	44.9	42.5	39.0
Anisaldehyde	60.0	59.7	54.5	53.2	51.4	48.0

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